

WARMING-UP EXERCISES IN LISTENING CLASSES

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ABSTRACT

Most of first-year students complain that they are bored doing the same thing from the beginning to the end of a listening class. When they do not feel interested in a subject such as listening skill in class, they do not get better their learning a language. Unluckily, many teachers who teach listening skill do not attend to whether students feel interested in listening to subject or not and motivate the students' activities that they provide in listening classes. I realize that it is necessary to find out how to keep student's attention in listening class. When I use warming-up activities in listening classes, I see that it is an easy way to bring variation in activities of listening class and to make the students curious of lesson. When they focus their attention on topic, it brings them purpose and motivation.

In this research, I find out that the effectiveness of using warming-up exercises in listening class is very important. It gives an introduction emphasizing on warming-up exercise or leading question that has a number of benefits. I often start a listening class with a warming-up exercise that may encourage interest among students, make a friendly environment, increase students' participation, attract their attention etc. During more 10 years of teaching listening period, I find out that warming-up exercise plays an important role in listening class and it is helpful for me and my students in teaching foreign language especially listening skill. After getting students' opinion, the result of the survey showed that it is helpful to use a warming-up exercises in listening classes.

1 INTRODUCTION

The article is about how to motivate students in listening classes. I am a teacher of English of Ho Chi Minh City University of Food Industry (HUPI). My students are from elementary to pre-intermediate level. Except for students at the elementary level, all of the college students coming to school start learning English at the pre-intermediate level. Although they – college students – are at pre-intermediate, most of them are poor in English, except some students. The number of students is considered having enough ability to follow the course makes up 1 or 1.5 percent of the total of the class. As a matter of fact, listening to English is a skill is not easy for students who do not like English majors, especially in a big class with more than 60 students. Most students in my class are very bored and nervous about the listening lesson. They always complain that they do not get any benefit from long and boring listening lessons. To me, as teaching English, I always toss and turn every day how I can do to improve the current situation of my listening class. I really see the necessity to make listening lessons to become more and more exciting and how to motivate my students' enthusiasm are not good at listening skill so that they can make progress in studying listening lessons.

Like all colleagues of the Department of Foreign language, I can see clearly that listening lessons are not often welcome in the class. Boring eyes exposed to feelings of nervous and forcing, when I come to the class with a CD-player in my hand. To try to reduce the nervous and boring on their faces, I often start my lecture by keeping their attention on review-questions relating to old lesson just to discuss. Like this way, I also connect/add to some questions relating to listening lesson today. Frequently, students do not recognize the purpose of discussion that is helpful for their listening comprehension lesson. And it is the time all of them forget that they are here for listening lessons. But it is not easy to follow this way, because it requires full of energetic teacher and even it takes too much time to do. In most public universities in Vietnam, time spends on each skill not enough to help teachers and students work together for progress.

On the other hand, in all universities in Vietnam that English is not a major subject and in the final test that listening skill is not required. For the reason, most students feel lazy and boring with listening comprehension lessons, they let them go out in their listening course. Although they always want to get a promotion in their English ability, they do not want to learn the listening skill. To them, listening is a difficult skill and it requires learners must pay more attention to practice, and even they have to spend uninspired time to practice alone. For the reason, besides time for practicing in class, there is no time for listening at home. I totally understand that most of students have looked back on listening topic with fear and often complained that they get benefit little by listening lessons.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 The Importance of Warming-Up Exercises

2.1.1 What is leading question?

Leading question is a firstly warming-up step which helps the students who learn listening skill that becomes less tense and also makes a more positive mood in graduating students that they get in the listening later. "Warming-up stage is a short activity for the beginning of a listening lesson". I realize that warming-up exercises are beneficial activities that help the students begin to think a lot of English listening lessons, especially previously introduced materials and become interested in the lesson. According to me, leading question is the "initial orientation". So, the leading question is one of activities which used to start listening lessons with interesting tasks that help the students feel comfortable in the classroom and to make them think of listening lessons effectively.

2.1.2 Why is the leading question important?

The leading question is the first kind of question form that is very important in teaching listening skill because it gives the following purposes.

2.1.2.1 Setting up a comfortable Relationship

In the learning process, as an English teacher teaching listening skill I should create a comfortable atmosphere by asking leading questions a positive relationship with all students. An interesting class nearly depends on the way that I do. Because of my teaching method, I motivate the students to build a positive attitude in learning listening skill. Teacher's manner is an important factor to make a friendly relationship between students and teachers. If the teaching method is easy to understand, the learning condition is good. I attempted to set a comfortable atmosphere in listening class by choosing certain types of exercises and questions relating to listening lessons. I also shared their difficult problems in students' lessons by growing rapport with them. So building up a

sense of relationship and mutual affection among the teacher and the students is the firstly step to create a comfortable and friendly atmosphere in classroom, “rapport is the ability to build trust and confidence with others, often when there is little time available”. Leading questions and using puzzle pictures in the teaching process are the way made for listening lessons to become interesting and would help the teacher to have a pleasant atmosphere in class. Leading question exercises such as joke, game, puzzle set up a positive learning environment and give the students chances to take part in listening lesson enthusiastically. When I showed pictures in front of the class, and then asked them some helpful questions regarding to the listening topic, my students were very excited, and they seemed to be motivated with warming-up exercises I made for listening lesson. I think that in the listening class, students need to share assignment with each other and how to use new technology to learn listening skill quickly. Warming-up exercises help to create a comfortable atmosphere and have equal confidence among students which allows them to carry negotiation in their activities easily. As an English teacher for 10 years, I would be aware of the usefulness of leading question exercises especially for the first lesson of any new class where students get an opportunity to know each other and I get a chance to understand the general level of the class. The kinds of leading question exercises create a kindly connection in the class.

2.1.2.2 Motivation and Warming-up

After five or ten minutes for asking leading questions, the students will become more self-confident in listening lessons of the beginning of a class. The learners’ interest is influenced by the class activities relating to English listening lessons. I think that many students will like to learn when the activities and exercises of leading questions are exciting. So, the leading question activity is taught like a method to motivate students learning listening skill exciting and successfully. According to me, motivated activity is students’ interest and enthusiasm when studying listening skill. Moreover the topics and tasks used in class are very important because it shows students’ levels of attention, and enjoyment. In the preparation step, a leading question will be acted as an essential thing to awaken students’ interest. I also mention that an interesting motivation and exploration help to expand listening skill and to have confidence in the learning process. Opening a new class with leading question activity is an easy way to improve students’ curiosity and attention and encourage them in the activities and exercises of listening classes.

2.1.2.3 Attention and Warming-up

I realize that uninteresting topics are in the students’ mind for short time and it is the taking possession by the mind in clear and do not get processed in their thoughts when lacking of attention and noticing. Opening lesson with activity and exercise mainly is a good way to used to focus the students’ attention on the lesson. I think that all teachers when teaching listening skill should give a more positive and serious learning attitude among the students and teacher. Of course, listening comprehension is a complicated skill that demands students’ tenacious efforts in practicing everyday to make progress. To help students have more interested in listening subject, I must stimulate their curiosity and attract their attention while doing leading questions and exercises relating to listening materials. Students will learn about English listening lessons better when they pay attention but do not learn much when they have lack of attention. I totally understand that focusing on the main ideas of the listening lesson is necessary. Firstly I prepare warming-up activity for my students for engaging them in interactive exercises to practice. The warming-up activities are used to keep students’ attention when they carry out their fully works especially ‘listening subject’. So, when using the warming-up activity, students’ concentration of the lesson would increase in more density and they would be invited to start thinking of listening topics. At the

beginning I do not know what and how I have to do. I really spent a new teaching experience with this kind of job. When working in pairs in a lesson, I and my students in class learned the way to cooperate together to make a good lesson and support each other during teaching presentation. For example: my partner and I could sample first for students to imitate in an activity in which there are two students working together for discussion or conversation. I appreciated that it should try to make clear what students will have to do before giving the topic to keep their attention. I understood that the warming-up activities like using pictures to show in front of the class is big enough to see clearly and help my students reduce their distraction in learning time and bring their concentration on the listening topics quickly.

2.2 How to motivate students in listening classes

In fact I found them interesting, but it is not totally appropriate to all classes because of students' poor vocabulary. When I showed picture in front of the class, and then asked them some helpful questions regarding to the listening lesson, my students were very excited to the picture and guiding questions, they seemed to be motivated with warming-up exercises I made for listening lesson, but they did not give any answers for this part. I attempted to get their answers by letting them say in Vietnamese in friendly and comfortable atmosphere. There were a lot of ideas of the answers which must be spoken in Vietnamese. They have become so accustomed to being allowed to express their thoughts in Vietnamese, that they have no real reason or motivation to learn more English vocabulary. They know they can tell you, "I must speak in Vietnamese; I do not have enough English vocabulary". So, they are permitted to speak Vietnamese. If they no longer will be allowed to speak Vietnamese all the time in class, then they will have to learn some more English phrases. This is the problem I was in teaching process. But I have obtained some new techniques of teaching listening from my partners. I also have got some specific comments that are very useful for my teaching listening skill individually such as how to keep my students' interest in their learning is very necessary. I just demonstrate problems I have ever met when using the approaches mentioned in the article. In my opinion, teachers have to keep patience and full of energy during teaching of listening process in the big classes with frequently over 60 students. As a matter of fact, warming-up exercises are the activities that help to improve students' interest and help students like their listening subject. It is not a test stage while listening, "In this process of doing the warn-up activity, students could build on their prior knowledge and at the same time, use vocabulary and structures that are connected with a particular function".

To the problems discussed above. Of course, listening comprehension is a complicated skill that demands learner's tenacious efforts in practicing everyday to make progress. So, English teachers should make lots of different kind of warn-up exercises and all exercises used during while-listening stage. Listening is one of the skills that demands to be taught with highly motivation in a lively atmosphere between the teacher and the students. This is a method that will help students feel interested and enjoy listening course

In my thoughts, it should have a tie of listening test at the end of the course. It is also a motivation to improve their present learning situation to listening comprehension skill. Because it is a way that helps students are aware of learning listening lessons in class consciously.

According to me "motivation is a basic principle of all kinds of teaching – the language student is best motivated by practice in which he senses the language is truly communicative, that it is appropriate to its context, that his teacher's skills are moving him forward to a fuller competence in the foreign language.". I totally agree with the ways mentioned in the article such as: questions and answers, using pictures, reading stories.

2.2.1 Questions and Answers

I really realize that when I ask questions relating to listening lesson I met technical matters such as grammar and vocabulary. But to the first-year students, it is not easy to ask students all the questions in English. As a teacher, I should choose the topics or situations that are appropriate with students' level and age for discussing easily. Listening comprehension needs to have learners' participation enthusiastically, because every immediate feedback of students helps to keep their interest and motivation through learning process. I have given to those first five to ten minutes for "Questions and Answers" to motivate students' curiosity. Before listening to difficult passages, I always ask some lively questions so that students have some ideas about the topic. In this process of doing leading questions, I use vocabulary and grammar structures that are connected with a particular function of listening lesson. I think they have become so accustomed to being allowed to express their thoughts in English language that they learned.

For example:

- What are the main differences between having a job and going to university?
- Do you often go to cinema?
- Do you like table-tennis?

2.2.2 Using pictures

As an English teacher of listening skill, I often use pictures and guiding questions in my listening class. Because the pictures create favorable conditions for students to prepare their knowledge, vocabulary, psychology before they pay attention to listen to the content of the topic. Pictures will bring the real images for students of the listening class. Because students do not have any ideas to talk or listen about the topic if they are put in the situation in which they never have any experience. Pictures are useful in improving my students' skill, especially 'directed listening'. The pictures were not only to help the student' listening comprehension highly, but also they can provide a general background and meaning of lesson. The pictures especially contribute to through my teaching process to get students' interest and motivation. I see that the point of view is very interesting and sound strange for me and my students when showing pictures in front of the class with listening lesson.

For example, find out this "spot the similarity" exercises.

- Ask my students to work in pairs or groups, to provide each student or pairs with pictures regarding to the topic that the other(s) must not see.
- Tell my students paintings of each student and pairs are very different from each other, so ask them to describe their paintings following the different styles they can.
- After several minutes of preparing knowledge for listening, I ask my students to look at the two paintings and make questions about the pictures. Then I would find out what other similarities they can have. Such as I will listen to my students' description of faces, facility symbols, maps that they understand from listening lesson. I realized that my students were very happy to have the chance to listen, speak, and do something lively in the listening class. I appreciate that each student must make more efforts by self in designing his/her own lesson. Through my individual experience, I got some comments that are helpful for my teaching in university. I should make clear when I ask my students work in the activity in

which it requires students not talking or discussing just thinking about what students are going to say about the listening topic.

2.2.3 Reading stories

Reading stories in listening class is also a good method that I have used when teaching listening skill. Stories, if well-told or attractive, are listened to by most students, and are particularly popular with all students whose listening abilities are lower than intermediate level in English. I often use stories with humorous content and easy to understand with simple vocabulary that taken from 'Basic or simple stories for transcription'. Before my students listened to the tape, I read an interesting story in low speed with one or two times, and then I asked my students some questions about the story or tell them retold the story in their own words. I suggest the end of the story students need to give idea to discuss, and they would finish the story by their own words. Almost students liked the lively activities in the class since they were interested in the humorous stories that I told in English and they got benefits from the listening experience. Especially the students who were very poor in English listening skill, they were surprised and funny when understanding some English stories easily. Moreover, telling the stories in English would improve students' listening skill, and I understand learning foreign language is not just only as a listening subject, but also can be a source of enjoyment and recreation. Telling the humorous stories is a kind of game that really created a funny and fresh atmosphere in listening class. All students were attracted on this game lively.

The above listening activities as warming-up exercises or leading questions were used as a tool to promote students' interest and help my students who study listening lessons to like listening skill more. The activities and exercises of opening would give a good result about students' listening ability and make them want to listen and speak English language more. After some weeks to make a practice of listening lesson, the students in my class had better understanding and speaking ability. I see that the students have the habit of listening to English after class to practice such as listening to music, tapes and so on, so they are good at listening skill quickly, especially English stories.

3 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

3.1 Conclusion

As a teacher of English especially listening skill, I reflect on some of current aspects existing in teaching process in university. To the issues discussed above, of course, it partly provides necessary information that helps me have a better and clearer look in teaching listening lessons. I hope with interesting activities like using pictures, telling lively stories, asking questions regarding to the topic which are the good method for my students to express their opinion of what they listened. I used warming-up exercises and leading questions in teaching process like the new teaching methods to get successful result for my listening class. The result of learning listening skill has showed that in a language classroom, warming-up exercises should be performed many times in listening class regularly. One of the reasons of using warming-up method is to establish emotional relationship between students and teachers, and to make a confidence that enough to help students reduce nervous and pressure to produce their ideas in the best way. To create a comfortable learning atmosphere for the students in listening class, I attempted to help my students less stress while listening English firstly in the class. So, I chose warming-up exercises as a good way to motivate the students study in my listening class. The warming-up method is also a kind of

good exercise for the students to recall their background knowledge. As well as other teachers, I discuss the main objectives of lesson in the warming-up section so that students get a clear goal and have higher effort in learning listening skill. However, this paper has showed every teacher uses warming-up method for different purposes of listening lesson. I would use warming-up method to get students' concentration, but others use it to activate students' activity in communication and to make a good relationship to motivate the students' professional ability. If warming-up method is a difficult thing to do, the students will be uninterested to study with that activity, when I will not evaluate their professional skill. Using a simple method in the first listening lessons helps my students understand the content of lesson easily and encourage them participate in further activities of class.

3.2 Recommendations

1. Although the warming-up is a preparation for physical effort in through learning process, many teachers still neglect their duty. Instead of firstly teaching the class with the main content, I would use the warming-up activity to make the listening class more lively and friendly before let students listen to the lesson. The students do not pay attention in class when they find boring from lessons. The warming-up activity will bring funny atmosphere in class and get the students' concentration better.
2. After teaching for a long time in observed class, I had full of energy in my classes. I would try to create a lively atmosphere class to keep students' motivation, but it should be really serious class during learning time.
3. After teaching listening skill for many years in university, I reflect on some of current aspects existing in teaching and learning listening English. To the issues discussed above, Of course, it partly provides necessary information that helps me and my colleagues have a better and clearer look in teaching listening lessons. My Students would have chances to listen and share their ideas with each other in leading questions and the warming-up activities in the listening classes. I provide them individual works to help them feel interest and enjoy listening subject more.
4. I can see clearly that listening lessons are not often welcome in the class. Boring eyes exposed to feeling s of nervous and forcing, when I come to the class on the first day with a CD-player in my hand. So it is necessary to start listening lesson with the warming-up activity because it is a kind of exercise makes my listening classes more interesting.

REFERENCES

- [1] Lin Lougheed (2013). Listening and Reading. Longman Preparation Series For The Toeic Test.
- [2] Koh Myounghee, Park Younghwal, Park Kyubyong, Choi Eunjung, Lee Hyunju, Carey Groleau, Henry John Amen IV (2008). Ivy's Listening 15 Actual Tests Toefl iBT.
- [3] Best, J. W., & Kahn, J. V. (1986). Research in Education. New Delhi: Prentice-Hall of India Pvt. Ltd, 5th edition.
- [4] Brown, S. (2006). Teaching Listening. Cambridge, NY: Cambridge University Press.
- [5] Carrell, P. L. (1983). Some Issues in Studying the Role of Schemata, or Background Knowledge, in Second Language Comprehension. Reading in a foreign language.

- [6] Cheung, C. K. (2001). The use of popular culture as a stimulus to motivate secondary students' English learning in Hong Kong.
- [7] Eragamreddy, N. (2013). Teaching Creative Thinking Skills. *IJ-ELTS: International Journal of English Language & Translation Studies*.
- [8] Farrell, T. S. C. (2008). Critical incidents in ELT initial teacher training. *ELT Journal*.
- [9] García, A. M., & Martín, J. C. (2004). Something Old and Something New. Techniques to Improve the Lexical Inventory of EST Students: A Proposal. *Revista Estudios Ingleses*.
- [10] Hasan, M. K., & Akhand, M. M. (2013). Strategies for Enhancing the Use of Textbooks in Language Classrooms at the Tertiary Level. *ABAC Journal*.
- [11] Joshi, M. (2006). Diversity in Lecture-Delivery. *Journal of NELTA*.
- [12] Klippel, F. (1985). *Keep Talking: communicative fluency activities for language teaching*. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press.